

CHALLENGE AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR FRICTION STIR WELDING OF DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Friction stir welding (FSW) is a promising joining process for discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (DRMMCs). In this article, current state of understanding and development of FSW for a wide range of DRMMCs are viewed, including microstructural evolution, mechanical properties, and tool wear, etc.

Keywords: metal matrix composite, friction stir welding, particle, microstructure, wear

1. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (DRMMCs) exhibit improved stiffness, strength, wear resistance and reduced coefficient of thermal expansion over monolithic alloys and have potential structural applications in the aerospace and automotive industries [1]. However, the weldability of these composites is significantly reduced due to the addition of ceramic reinforcements. It is hard to achieve defect-free DRMMC welds [2,3]. The drawbacks associated with the fusion welding include: (a) the incomplete mixing of the parent and filler materials, (b) the presence of porosity as large as 100 μm in the fusion zone, (c) the excess eutectic formation, and (d) the formation of undesirable deleterious phases such as Al_4C_3 . Therefore, a solid state welding technique is highly desirable for joining MMCs [4].

Friction stir welding (FSW) is a novel solid-state joining technique, particularly applied in aerospace and automotive industries [4]. In the welding process, localized heating, resulted from friction between the tool and workpieces, softens the material around the pin, and the combination of tool rotation and translation results in movement of material from the front to the back of the pin, thereby producing a welded joint in solid state. Therefore, FSW is considered a promising welding technique for joining the DRMMCs to avoid the drawbacks of the fusion welding.

In the last few years, a number of investigations [5-7] have been conducted to join the DRMMCs by FSW. While higher joint efficiency of 70-90% could be obtained in the FSW DRMMC joints, two important challenges must be faced. First, the DRMMCs exhibit lower ductility than the monolithic alloys even at high temperatures. Therefore, the optimum FSW parameters for producing sound welds were generally limited to lower tool traverse speeds. Second, severe wear of the steel tool occurred during FSW due to the presence of hard ceramic reinforcements. This not only reduced the lifetime of the tool, but also affected the properties of the FSW welds adversely, due to the

existence of the wear debris. Clearly, compared to monolithic alloys, it is difficult to achieve sound MMC welds via FSW. In this article, current state of understanding and development of FSW for the DRMMCs are viewed.

2. MICROSTRUCTURE OF FSW DRMMC JOINTS

2.1 Macrostructure of nugget zone

Similar to FSW aluminum alloys, the FSW DRMMC joints consisted of three zones: nugget zone (NZ), thermomechanically affected zone (TMAZ), and heat affected zone (HAZ). Fig. 1 shows a typical cross-sectional macrograph of FSW SiCp/2009Al joint welded at a rotation rate of 600 rpm and a traverse speed of 50 mm/min by the cylindrical pin [5]. The NZ exhibited an elliptical shape and onion rings were distinctly visible. Although the shape of the NZ was different for various tool shapes and FSW parameters, some similar macrostructural features were observed in various FSW composite joints. For example, the onion rings were generally observed in the NZ. Marzoli et al [8] reported that the onion rings were mainly visible on the retreating side of the NZ in FSW 20%Al₂O₃p/6061Al composite joint and considered that the material flow of the aluminium matrix was partially hindered by the alumina particles, and the recrystallization in the NZ was not complete in this case. Uzun [9] and Storjohann et al. [2] found that the onion rings in the NZ of FSW SiCp/2124Al and Al₂O₃p/6061Al composite joints consisted of segregated fine reinforcement particles within the onion ring bands and exhibited the alternating regions of high and low fine reinforcement particles density. However, for the FSW SiCp/2009Al [5], the onion rings consisted of fine Al-Cu-Fe-Mg and Al-Cu-Fe phase particle-rich bands, and the SiC particles did not segregate in the onion rings. This is attributed to that high strain rate gradient was not sufficient to drive the large SiC particles to segregate to the high density bands of particles.

Fig. 1 Optical macrograph showing transverse cross-section of FSW SiCp/2009Al joint welded at a rotation rate of 600 rpm and a traverse speed of 50 mm/min [5].

2.2 Reinforcement particle distribution in nugget zone

For the base materials (BM), the reinforcement particle clusters were often observed [9,10]. After the FSW, the particle distribution in the NZ was significantly improved. The particle clusters were broken up and the particle distribution became homogeneous due to the intense plastic deformation and material mixing in the NZ. Furthermore, the size of the particles decreased in the NZ and the edges and corners of the particles were obviously blunted due to the cracking of some large and knocking off of sharp corners and edges from the large particles resulting from the stirring breaking effect of the threaded tools. Fig. 2 shows the particle distribution in the NZ and BM of the FSW Al₂O₃p/6061Al composite. It is apparent that after FSW, the sharp edges and corners of the particles disappeared and the number of fine particles increased in the NZ. Similar

phenomena were observed in the other FSW DRMMCs such as SiCp/2009Al and SiCp/2124Al [5,9].

Fig. 2 Particle distribution in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/6061\text{Al}$ composite: (a) BM, (b) NZ [8].

2.3 Recrystallization and variation of precipitates in nugget zone

Similar to that of the monolithic alloys, the NZ of the FSW DRMMC joints also consisted of the fine equiaxed recrystallized grains [4]. This suggests that dynamic recrystallization (DRX) occurred in the NZ of the FSW DRMMCs. The reinforcement particles had a large effect on the recrystallization behavior [11]. The DRX nucleated in regions of very high dislocation density between the reinforcements [12]. Inem [11] found that the SiC particles provided more nucleation sites for the newly recrystallized grains by increasing local strain in the matrix and causing lattice misorientation. The particles play an important role in controlling the recrystallized grain size by particle stimulated nucleation. In addition, the reinforcement particles would inhibit the growth of the recrystallized grains. Feng et al [5] reported that the FSW SiCp/2009Al composite exhibited a grain size of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ in the NZ, which was significantly refined compared to that of the BM. After a post-T4 treatment, the grain size of the NZ increased to $8.0 \mu\text{m}$, indicating that the fine-grains in the composites were relatively stable. By comparison, abnormal grain growth was often observed in the FSW aluminium alloys.

There were few reports about the variation of precipitates in the FSW DRMMC joints. Feng et al [5] reported the coarse θ (Al_2Cu) phase particles in the extruded SiCp/2009Al plate disappeared in the NZ after FSW and some fine θ'' phase particles were observed. This indicated that FSW resulted in the dissolution of the coarse θ phase particles, which is the equilibrium phase for the 2009Al alloys, and subsequent natural aging led to the precipitation of the fine θ'' phase particles. After the T4 treatment, the number of the θ'' phase increased and the some needle-shaped S' phase (Al_2CuMg) were observed in the NZ. However, the variation of the precipitates in other zones such as HAZ and TMAZ was not reported. This needs additional investigation.

3. TOOL WEAR

A critical problem associated with FSW of the DRMMCs is severe wearing of the FSW tool due to the presence of hard ceramic reinforcements. Table 1 summarizes the reported

tool wearing during FSW for various DRMMCs. It is clear that the FSW tools made from tool-steel exhibited serious wear in the welding process of the DRMMCs. Nelson et al. [13] observed that for the threaded tool made from H13 tool steel, heat-treated to $R_c > 52$, on FSW of $B_4Cp/6061Al$ composite at a tool rotation rate of 670 rpm and a traverse speed of 114-138 mm/min, no threads were left on the pin and the shoulder was worn out by approximately 2 mm in less than 254 mm of weld. SEM backscattered images revealed that the wear debris from the tool was deposited through the thickness of the $B_4Cp/6061Al$ weld and on the surface of the weld in particular. It was suggested that the wear debris would affect the quality of the weld and reduce the properties.

More recently, Prado et al. [14] investigated the tool wear behavior in FSW of $Al_2O_3p/6061Al$ composite. For O1 tool-steel threaded pin, heat-treated to an R_c hardness of 62, at a tool rotation rate of 500-2000 rpm and a traverse speed of 60 mm/min, while no apparent tool wear was noted for FSW of 6061Al, severe tool wear occurred for FSW of $Al_2O_3p/6061Al$ composite. The wear rate of the tool increases linearly with increasing linear welding distance. The largest wear rate was observed at a tool rotation rate of 1000 rpm. This means that the wear rate of tool did not increase when the tool rotation rate was increased above 1000 rpm. A possible reason for this is the improvement of flow properties of the composite at high tool rotation rate due to increased thermal input.

Table 1 Tool wearing of various FSW DRMMC joints achieved at different parameter.

Materials	Particle Vf (%)	Rotation rate (rpm)	Traverse speed (mm/min)	Tool Material	Wearing of tool	Welding distance (mm)
SiCp/2009Al [9]	25	800	120	TiAlN-coated HSS-steel	-	-
$Al_2O_3p/7005Al$ [10]	10	600	300	Ferro-Titanit alloy	-	-
$B_4Cp/6061Al$ [13]	15-30	670	114-138	H13 tool steel	Serious	254
$Al_2O_3p/6061Al$ [14]	20	500-2000	60	Standard tool steel	Serious	310
SiCp/2009Al [15]	15	600	50	H13 tool steel	Serious	-
SiCp/AC4A Al [16]	30	1500-2000	25-150	WC-Co hard alloy	Normal	240
SiCp/A359 [18]	20	1000	180-540	Standard tool steel	Serious	610
SiCp/A356 [19]	15	1200	30	D2 tool steel	-	60

Feng et al. [15] reported that the Fe wore by the hard and sharp SiC particles formed the Cu_2FeAl_7 phase around the SiC particles, when SiCp/2009Al was FSWed by a steel tool. Two type of the Cu_2FeAl_7 were identified in the NZ, i.e. the single-crystal Cu_2FeAl_7 phase around the SiC particles and the polycrystalline nanostructured Cu_2FeAl_7 phase on the interface of the SiC particles with a specifically crystallographic orientation relationship $(1012)_{SiC} \parallel (212)_{Cu_2FeAl_7}$ [15]. The Cu_2FeAl_7 particle formed at the interface of the SiC particle might reduce the interfacial bonding between SiC and aluminum matrix. Furthermore, the formation of Cu_2FeAl_7 phase reduced the amount of the precipitates in the matrix due to the dilution of Cu. Both of these two factors decreased the mechanical properties of the FSW composite joints [15].

To reduce the tool wear, some hard materials were used to produce the welding tools (Table 1). Ceschini et al. [10] used the Ferro-Titanit alloy to weld the $Al_2O_3p/7A10Al$

composite. The strength of the joints was 81% of the BM. However, the wearing of the tools was not reported. Furthermore, Liu et al. [16] used the WC-Co hard alloy tools to weld the SiCp/AC4A Al at the tool rotation rates of 1500-2000 rpm and the traverse speeds of 25-150 mm/min. The wearing rate of the tool increased with decreasing the welding speed. The maximum wear rate was always produced in the initial welding process. For example, after an initial welding was performed at a welding speed of 25 mm/min, the pin diameter decreased at most by 11%. After the seventh welding was performed, 27% of the pin diameter at the maximum-wear location disappeared. In addition, Prado et al. [17] and Shindo et al. [18] found that the tool wearing in the FSW process of Al₂O₃p/6061Al and SiCp/359Al composites produced a self-optimized shape which resulted in excellent welds and no additional tool wear when that was achieved. This provides a new idea for the geometry design of the welding tool.

Fig. 3 TEM images of NZ of FSW SiCp/2009Al composite showing Cu₂FeAl₇ phase, with inserts showing selected-area diffraction pattern of Cu₂FeAl₇ [15].

4. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FSW DRMMC JOINTS

4.1 Hardness profiles

Similar to the heat treatable Al alloys, the hardness profile of the cross section of the FSW composite joints was influenced by the heat input [9,20]. Fig. 4 shows the hardness profiles of the FSW SiCp/2124Al-T4 joint [9]. The micro-hardness profiles were measured across the FSW cross-section at the top (1 mm from the top surface), the middle and the root (1 mm from the bottom surface) of the plate. A similar trend was observed in the three hardness profiles. Similar to the FSW heat treatable monolithic alloys [20], the HAZ exhibited the lowest hardness due to the coarsening and dissolution of the strengthening precipitates, whereas the hardness of the NZ was lower than that of the BM due to the fundamental dissolution of the precipitates.

4.2 Tensile properties

Table 2 summarizes the transverse tensile properties of various FSW composite joints. The ultimate tensile properties (UTS) of the joints could reach up to 70.7%-90.0% of

the BMs. The joint efficiencies were significantly higher than those achieved by other welding methods [3]. There were several factors affecting the tensile properties of the FSW composite joints. Ceschini et al. [10] produced the FSW $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/7075\text{Al}$ joint at a high traverse speed of 300 mm/min and obtained a joint efficiency of 82%, which was attributed to the welding defect in the NZ due to the high traverse speed of welding. Feng et al. [5] reported that under a post-weld T4 treatment, the UTS of the FSW joint of extruded $\text{SiCp}/2009\text{Al}$ composite was lower than that of the BM. This was attributed to the formation of the Cu_2FeAl_7 phase around the SiC particles [5,15]. Marzoli et al. [8] prepared the FSW $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/6061\text{Al}$ joints by using ultra-hardness material tools. No tool wear and welding defects in the NZ were reported. Similar to the FSW Al alloy [20], the composite joints failed in the HAZ with the lowest hardness due to the coarsening of the precipitates and the UTS of the joints was 70% of the BM.

Fig. 4 Hardness profiles of FSW $\text{SiCp}/2124\text{Al-T4}$ joints [9].

Table 2 Transverse tensile properties of various FSW DRMMC joints.

Materials	Particle Vf (%)	Rotation rate (rpm)	Traverse speed (mm/min)	UTS _{FSW} /UTS _{BM} (%)
$\text{SiCp}/2009\text{Al}$ [5]	15	600	50	90
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/6061\text{Al}$ [8]	20	400-700	150-500	70.7
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/7005\text{Al}$ [10]	10	600	300	82
$\text{B}_4\text{Cp}/6061\text{Al}$ [13]	15-30	670	114-138	84.4
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/6061\text{Al}$ [21]	20	800	56	86.8
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/7005\text{Al}$ [21]	10	800	56	83.9

4.3 Fatigue properties

For the DRMMCs, the typical failure mechanisms are: (i) cracking of large reinforcing particles, (ii) interfacial decohesion at the particle-matrix interface, resulting in nucleation of voids, and (iii) growth and coalescence of voids in the matrix [22,23]. The information about the fatigue properties of the FSW DRMMC joints is limited so far. Ceschini et al. [10] investigated the low-cycle fatigue of FSW $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/7005\text{Al}$ joint. The reinforcing particles were significantly broken up in the FSW process and distributed homogeneously in the NZ. In this case, the local stress was not high enough to crack the particles, and less cracked particles were observed on the failure surface compared to the BM. However, the welding defect, due to high traverse speed (300 mm/min),

decreased the fatigue life of the joints and the fatigue life of all the FSW joints was lower than that of the BM.

5. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

High quality FSW joints are significant for wide structural applications of the DRMMCs in view of technical and economical benefits. Improving the weldability and reducing the tool wear are the prerequisite for achieving high-quality FSW composite joints. Severe wear of the steel tool and the formation of undesirable phase resulting from the wearing debris indicated that the steel tool is not suitable for FSW of the composites. Therefore, it is highly desirable to adopt wear-resistant tool materials, such as polycrystalline cubic boron nitride (PCBN) [24], to avoid tool wear. Furthermore, surface hardening coating on the steel tool might be an alternate approach to increase wear resistance [25]. Due to limited investigations, it is necessary to establish the FSW window for various DRMMCs. Furthermore, the microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of the FSW DRMMCs need in-depth investigations. Although a number of challenges still exist, FSW offers very attractive possibilities for commercial success of joining of the DRMMCs.

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